

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D4.7 – Report on strategic learning in city twinning programmes

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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Executive summary

Twinning activities in UP2030 were essential peer-to-peer learning spaces that facilitated exchange of information, common problem solving, dissemination of key project or process information, learning from processes of peers, building capacity on key topics or concepts explored in the project, and created deep-dives into case studies from which other cities could learn.

In UP2030, there were four key types of learning activities organised to facilitate strategic learning and city twinning. Each activity served a specific purpose both in function and themes addressed. The ‘Office Hours’ facilitated essential pilot implementation and monitoring discussions, the ‘Peer review sessions’ supported learning between similar pilots on common challenges and activities, the ‘Learning Sessions’ explored the contextualisation of the 5UP approach across all the pilots, and the ‘Knowledge Exchange event’ created a crucial mid-project milestone to facilitate cross-pilot exchange and learning.

This deliverable documents the key achievements and outcomes across all the learning activities, reflects on the challenges and opportunities of implementing such learning activities and finally provides recommendations for organising similar activities in the future based on the experience of the UP2030 partners.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the work packages (WPs) structure. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with all Pilot Cities and City Liaison partners. The following table lists the deliverables and milestones that were input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content here presented.

Input from	Contributes to
T2.3 City & stakeholder engagement for the identification of needs for upgrading, barriers and drivers of change	Mil.4: Cities have set-up LAAs Mil. 5: Cities run first workshop on needs
T2.4 Co-designing pilot shared visions and adaptive pathways for transformation	Mil. 6: Cities run second workshop on vision Mil. 7: Cities establish user stories
T3.1 Roadmap implementation through solution integration	Mil. 9: City "Partnership Commitments"
T3.4 Tools and approaches for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice	Mil. 10: Cities run third workshop on action Mil. 11: Major city twinning "knowledge exchange" event
T4.1 Pilots coordination & implementation of solutions & processes	Mil. 13: All cities have at least one successful prototype
T4.2 Learning and Action Alliances’ setup and activities	Mil.14: Cities run fourth workshop on upscale
T4.4 Cross-pilot exchange Community of Practice and Strategic Learning	D2.1 – The 5UP approach and its contextualisation in the project cities
T5.1 Enabling governance environment, integrative policy development	D2.4 – An interactive toolkit for stakeholder engagement in co-design of visions and pathways towards climate neutrality
T5.3 Financing the transition	

<p>T6.2 Dissemination and communication actions</p>	<p>D3.3 – Transformative pathways roadmaps: strategic integration of solutions and interoperability 3</p> <p>D2.5 – Report on vision co-design methodology report and its application for pilot shared visions</p> <p>D4.2 – UP2030 implementation plan for the pilot cities 2</p> <p>D4.3 – Sustained engagement strategy of Learning & Action Alliances to promote the neutrality vision in the UP2030 pilots</p> <p>D4.6 – Report on monitoring, evaluation and KPI validation in the 5UP-approach implementation pilots 3</p> <p>D5.2 – Analysis and recommendations for transformative governance and policy 2</p>
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The learning activities organised in UP2030 served four essential functions: (1) monitoring project and pilot implementation, (2) facilitating exchange between similar pilots, (3) facilitating discussion on the tailoring of the 5UP approach to each pilot and (4) hosting a knowledge exchange event which supported cross-pilot learning. Needless to say, these activities were central to key tasks in the project that were responsible for developing different resources, methods and knowledge to be tailored in cities. This deliverable is the final report for activities carried out under T4.4: Cross-pilot exchange Community of Practice and Strategic Learning. This task facilitated cross-WP and cross-city exchange drawing input from the tasks listed above and contributing to the achievements of a number of milestones and deliverables listed. Note that due to its central position to different partners, cities, and tasks within the process, this report both received and provided input to all tasks in the project, either directly or indirectly.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
BoTu	Bospolder-Tussendijken – pilot area in Rotterdam
D	Deliverable
ICLEI	ICLEI European Secretariat GMBH
LAA	Learning Action Alliance
M	Month
Mil.	Milestone
MfC	Mapping for Change
R-Cities	Resilient Cities Network
TSPA	Thomas Stellmach Planning and Architecture
UIC	Universitat Internacional de Catalunya
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

Several EU-funded projects such as NetZeroCities, REACHOUT, UNP+, and others often involve multi-partner and multi-city collaboration. An integral element for successful project implementation is the establishment of meaningful and useful learning and exchange activities and communities of practice that not only guide the logistical, methodological and process-related aspects of the projects but also build capacity on the conceptual and thematic focus areas explored in different contexts.

Strategic learning and city twinning activities hence play a crucial role in ensuring that all partners understand the core concepts, milestones, and deadlines, and the approaches for co-creation, analysis, and assessments carried out through the project duration. Many cities face existing barriers of limited time and availability to participate effectively in learning activities, and extensive online collaboration increases participant's fatigue. It was important to keep these challenges in mind while designing knowledge exchange and capacity building activities. Hence, exploring a diverse range of strategic learning activities with varying formats, content, and levels of engagement was crucial. UP2030 explores such strategy by identifying four key types of activities, each serving a purpose, whether process-based or content-driven. The first activity, the **Office Hours**, primarily focused on process and methodological discussions. The second, the **Peer Review sessions**, focused on bilateral exchange between cities working on similar topics or challenges. Note that in UP2030, the project did not follow a frontrunner/follower city setup and instead set up groups based on similar ambitions within the project. The third activity, the **Learning Sessions**, focused on the 5UP approach which has been tested for the first time in this project. And finally, the **Knowledge Exchange**, as a one-time 1.5 day event, integrated site visits and brainstorming workshops to steer the strategic direction and priorities across all the cities. These four types were defined at the start of the project, drawing insights and learning from other EU-funded projects as well as other examples on how to shape such strategic learning spaces for cities with different learning priorities (Campbell, 2009). Each activity had its own purpose, target group, and thematic focus, as well as collaborators across the project duration.

This report gives an overview of the activities that took place, captures their outcomes and key achievement and provides insight into how the activities supported the city's pilot implementation processes. At the end of the report, Resilient Cities Network (R-Cities) has captured reflections and takeaways from the experience of UP2030 and provides recommendations on how to build a strategy for twinning and peer-to-peer learning in multi-city programmes.

1.2 Document structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 – Introduction: description of the purpose, scope, and structure of the document.
- ❖ Section 2 – Strategic learning activities in UP2030: overview of the different types of activities carried out within UP2030 and key achievements
- ❖ Section 3 – Reflection and takeaways from the learning activities: Insights into challenges and impact created through the learning activities
- ❖ Section 4 – Recommendations: A strategy for facilitating twinning and peer-to-peer learning in multi-city programmes: Based on shared reflection with partners, a set of recommendations to consider while organising similar activities
- ❖ Section 5 – Conclusions: Summary of findings and recommendations

2 Strategic learning activities in UP2030

Twinning activities in UP2030 were essential peer-to-peer learning spaces that facilitated exchange of information, common problem solving, dissemination of key project or process information, learning from processes of peers, building capacity on key topics or concepts explored in the project, and created deep-dives into case studies from which other cities could learn.

At the start of the project, four different kinds of activities were defined namely Office Hours, Peer review sessions, Learning Sessions, and Knowledge Exchange. While each activity had its unique frequency, purpose, and scope, the different types of activities also complemented each other to establish connections between them. For example, while Office Hours focused on collective problem solving and project or process monitoring, similarities or common themes were then explored in the Peer review sessions. The following sections illustrate each twinning activity in detail.

2.1 Office Hours: Cities and Liaisons meetings

“Office hours” (later renamed as “Cities and Liaisons bi-monthly meetings”) were the most frequent activity, implemented approximately once every two months. These sessions provided cities with essential information on project processes, milestones, deadlines, organization of workshops and outcomes. In this space, cities connected on shared processes, learning not only from the Work Package 4 (WP4) leads who designed the pilot implementation process, but also other cities as the generic process was tailored to specific contexts. Cities could also use these sessions to ask a specific questions to their peers and later connect bilaterally with each other.

Figure 1: 2025 Planning tracker developed to guide Office Hour discussions

Figure 2: Example of how WP4 & WP5 activities were aligned during Office Hours

The main focus is on project and process updates. An example of the planning tracker used to monitor pilot activities through the Office Hours is seen above in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

At the beginning of each year, it was essential to establish key goals and a broader overview of the project structure, to allow cities to plan their time, efforts, and workshops accordingly. A key activity therefore involved keeping track of pilot implementation plans created in Task 4.1 (Pilots coordination & implementation of solutions & processes) and ensuring milestones and deliverables were met. Through this process, we monitored key achievements and finalization of all four phases in the project: Needs assessment, Vision, Action, and Upscale. As the city prototypes defined a key final outcome per city, it is within this task that progress was monitored and achieved.

At the same time, this Office Hours was also used to showcase good practices to be established within the project and build capacity on the ambitious co-creation processes to be implemented in each pilot. Figure 3 presents an example agenda from an Office Hour focused on Learning Action Alliance (LAA) and visioning methodology.

Agenda – 02.10.2023

- LAA challenges and opportunities for UP2030 cities **ICATALIST**
- Case study on community backlash arising from a lack of needs analysis & stakeholder ecosystem engagement and participation **Mapping for Change**
- What the Visioning process will look like **TSPA**
- What a Partnership Commitment looks like **Resilient Cities**

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Figure 3: Agenda from Office Hour in year 2 of the project

Created as the essential grounding space for cities and liaison partners and nicknamed as “City & Liaison Bi-monthly meetings”, the Office Hours provided an overview of all tasks and themes discussed within UP2030. Cutting across the WP structures, several tasks from WP2 to WP6 were discussed throughout these meetings over the course of the project. These meetings were hence an essential space to plan for all task contributions (both in terms of inputs and outputs).

2.2 Knowledge Exchange event in Rotterdam

Organised in the mid-point of the project duration, the Knowledge Exchange for cities in Rotterdam (Figure 4) in June 2024 (M18) played an important role in reflecting on the outcomes of the first two phases of the project (Needs assessment and Vision) and thereafter in identifying the “prototype” that all cities would work on as their final output in the remaining two phases (Action and Upscale).

Led by R-Cities, the event brought together all city pilots and select partners leading key activities within the project.

Figure 4: Knowledge Exchange in Rotterdam

The agenda and topics outlined in Table 1, explored an intensive 1.5 day programme exploring many opportunities for sharing of lessons learned, facilitate cross-pollination of ideas, and solutions across cities, and create spaces for real time problem solving.

Table 1: Agenda for Knowledge Exchange June 2024

Agenda Day 1 (3 June 2024)

- Plenary and welcome by R-Cities and Resilient Rotterdam team (Municipality of Rotterdam)
- Session 1: Cities’ cluster exchange on Visioning workshops, concepts for Partnership Commitments & next Engagement workshop steps led by TSPA, I-Catalist and ICLEI

- Session 2: Design of Neutrality Story Maps - workshop led by VUB and CERTH
- Wrap up and closing

Agenda Day 2 (4 June 2024)

- Introduction to Knowledge Exchange Day 2 led by Resilient Rotterdam & Resilient BoTu team
- Session 1: Living lab in BoTu - Visit to BoTu projects and walk through the neighborhood. Field visit to BoTu led by Resilient Rotterdam team.
- Session 2: Workshop on the 5UP approach and link to the action phase led by R-Cities, Fraunhofer, UIC and TSPA: A reflection on the 5UP approach and activities followed so far and building a common understanding in an interactive workshop format with the cities
- Session 3: Results of the Knowledge Exchange: In this session, participants will look back at the discussions and outputs of the knowledge Exchange. Each city supported by the technical partners will present their key takeaways and create a plan for the action phase
- Wrap up and closing

2.3 Peer review sessions

Organised twice a year, the Peer Review sessions created a space for cities to share and learn in smaller groups based on similar challenges, going in more depth on challenges discussed during Office Hours. The focus for these sessions was learning either on a 1-to-1 basis or in smaller groups of cities. Both online and in-person sessions were explored to maximise learning opportunities while also leveraging moments such as consortium meetings and General Assembly sessions.

Initially, these Peer Review sessions aimed to create learning moments between cities that share similar themes or experiences while navigating the four phases of the project. For example, after the first workshops on Needs Assessments, cities like Belfast and Rotterdam, which shared similar approaches on community engagement, and cities like Granollers and Milan, which shared similarities in the typology of neighbourhood regeneration projects, shared their findings with each other. Figure 5 below showcases an example from a peer-review session. Note that the Peer Review sessions were closely supported by the Engagement Taskforce set up within UP2030 for guiding cross-WP working and monitoring of activities. The Engagement Taskforce, led by R-Cities, was composed of I-Catalist, Mapping for Change (MfC), Thomas Stellmach Planning and Architecture (TSPA) and Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB).

Figure 5: Peer review session on outcomes of first needs assessment workshop

In the first 1.5 years of the project, Peer Review sessions were structured based on similarities in project themes and processes across Pilot cities. A key turning point was the definition of each city’s prototype in M18, which led to the identification of two groups of cities based on the typology of their prototypes. See groups of cities identified below in Table 2. These groups were also validated in the mid-term project reporting in M18.

Table 2: Two Groups of cities based on typology of prototypes for peer review sessions

Group 1: Cities working on knowledge and training resources	Group 2: Cities working on planning instruments and physical interventions
Belfast	Lisbon
Budapest	Granollers
Muenster	Istanbul
Rotterdam	Milan
Thessaloniki*	Zagreb
Rio de Janeiro	Thessaloniki*

*Note that Thessaloniki’s prototype (District Climate Action Plan) spans both knowledge building and planning instruments. Hence it fits well in both groups.

Once these two groups had been defined, they formed the underlying structure for the organization of additional Peer Review sessions, for instance a dedicated parallel session during the General Assembly in Zagreb in October 2024 (M22). Finally, they also formed the structure for the organization of the Learning Sessions for the 5UP approach elaborated in the next section.

2.5 Learning sessions

In the UP2030, a key research innovation is the testing of the 5UP methodology that has been tailored to each pilot city's implementation process. In this project, 11 cities explore innovative and multi-dimensional instruments for actioning climate neutral, resilience and just neighbourhoods using the 5UP approach, a systemic methodology with 5 dimensions: needs, policies, and instruments (UPDATE), capacity building (UPSKILL), prototyping, and piloting (UPGRADE), replicating, rolling out, or transferring success (UPSCALING), and engagement, communication, and dissemination (UPTAKE) (UP2030, 2023).

To explore how this contextualisation has taken place and to build capacity among cities, Learning Sessions were organised through a series of workshops and focus group discussions. While initially planned to be five meetings in total, with each meeting focusing on one aspect of the 5UP approach, the focus was later updated to structure sessions in a way that all five UPs were discussed in some form as a continuous and iterative in every session. This was due to a number of factors: since all five UPs were inherently connected, cities found it difficult to focus on one UP per session. The 5UPs were also easier to grasp as a continuous process rather than isolated concepts.

The Learning Sessions were organised at two moments. The first session was held during the Knowledge Exchange in Rotterdam in M18. A comprehensive worksheet per city to contextualize the 5UPs was developed as a workshop exercise. This worksheet (Figure 6 and Figure 7) connected the city's needs and visions, to their process along the 5UPs. Each city received guidance on how to match their process and activities to each step of the 5UP approach and reflect on how the approach has been tailored to their local contexts. This was the first capacity building session to not only introduce the 5UP approach but also brainstorm on how this has been translated into their own pilots.

VISION: To create a climate resilient neighbourhood that adapts and mitigates climate risks through increased greening, better sustainable transport and more energy efficient buildings to act as a beacon of success for other neighbourhoods.

Climate neutrality will be achieved in a fair and just way by involving the community, along with other stakeholders, to develop more sustainable, accessible and affordable transport, better quality of homes through retrofitting buildings, and access to good quality green space. The communities will become the champions and drivers of its success, with opportunities of training for green jobs, community management of public spaces and ambassadors for public and active travel. This requires a collaborative approach across all levels and departments of governance, the third sector and private organisations.

BELFAST'S PROTOTYPE (DERIVED FROM THE WIDER PLAN & VISIONING ACTIVITIES)

Through UP2030, Belfast seeks to create a framework that will be applied to all its regeneration projects that engages new planning, green infrastructure, play and co-design with young people. The framework will be specific to the East-Quater district, which has been identified of becoming the first sustainable and just business district in Northern Ireland. Lessons learned from the pilot will be used to identify opportunities to other neighbourhoods and across the concept of our own districts across the city. Furthermore, the municipality aims to address the fragmentation in terms of governance and delivery, embedding this project in the upcoming update of Belfast's Community Plan 'The Belfast Agenda'.

Belfast

Who is your audience? How would you sell your prototype to an audience? What is your pitch?

What contributions from UP2030 partners & tools would take your prototype to the next level?

What does the prototype look like? What does it seek to achieve?

*Prototype: These is the key output that each city working towards. These could be physical interventions, digital tools, products and new policies.

Activities as part of the broader UP2030 process. Let's reflect on what you have achieved already

UPDATE	UPSKILL	UPGRADE	UPSCALE	UPTAKE
<p>? Understand which processes, planning codes, policies should be urgently updated. Identify and address needs and barriers through East-Quater pilots.</p> <p>Developing an understanding and identifying potential links with business to better align needs, resources & get traction</p> <p>Identifying of specific pilot projects to be undertaken in East-Quater</p> <p>Identifying of specific pilot projects aligned on to be aligned with climate neutrality and digital ambition</p> <p>Secure shared pilot delivery amongst local authorities. Identify main/lead/department of pilot and how to be successful</p> <p>Secure that pilot delivery has different departments working together in the pilot process</p> <p>Do pilot projects in parallel with the regular planning process. For e.g. through the planning process</p> <p>Based on framework identified a pilot to be developed. How to be successful</p> <p>Developing of specific pilot projects</p>	<p>? Build capacities for urban planning and design transformation activities. Update the entire stakeholder ecosystem, from city departments to urban practitioners through to citizens.</p> <p>Applying and experimenting with new tools to create urban planning and solutions. Identify contributors to the pilot and how to be successful</p> <p>Do the above but in building capacity and all development of the pilot for the transformation activities</p> <p>Applying and experimenting with new tools to create urban planning and solutions. Identify contributors to the pilot and how to be successful</p> <p>Do the above but in building capacity and all development of the pilot for the transformation activities</p> <p>Applying and experimenting with new tools for creating a diversity of stakeholders and models. Identify contributors to the pilot and how to be successful</p> <p>Develop an urban planning process aligned to the pilot and how to be successful</p> <p>Is the development of new models/tools/techniques for a pilot project for pilot?</p>	<p>? Prototype the transformation in the pilot pilot sites and assess the city's wider stakeholder ecosystem.</p> <p>Building an understanding and identifying potential links with business to better align needs, resources & get traction</p> <p>Identifying of specific pilot projects to be undertaken in East-Quater</p> <p>Identifying of specific pilot projects aligned on to be aligned with climate neutrality and digital ambition</p> <p>Secure shared pilot delivery amongst local authorities. Identify main/lead/department of pilot and how to be successful</p> <p>Secure that pilot delivery has different departments working together in the pilot process</p> <p>Do pilot projects in parallel with the regular planning process. For e.g. through the planning process</p> <p>Based on framework identified a pilot to be developed. How to be successful</p> <p>Developing of specific pilot projects</p>	<p>? Develop solutions across scales, integrate across sectors. Present to updating needs by shaping governance arrangements and enabling of projects to financial resources</p> <p>Building an understanding and identifying potential links with business to better align needs, resources & get traction</p> <p>Identifying of specific pilot projects to be undertaken in East-Quater</p> <p>Identifying of specific pilot projects aligned on to be aligned with climate neutrality and digital ambition</p> <p>Secure shared pilot delivery amongst local authorities. Identify main/lead/department of pilot and how to be successful</p> <p>Secure that pilot delivery has different departments working together in the pilot process</p> <p>Do pilot projects in parallel with the regular planning process. For e.g. through the planning process</p> <p>Based on framework identified a pilot to be developed. How to be successful</p> <p>Developing of specific pilot projects</p>	<p>? Support uptake through knowledge transfer by offering the project's services to the citizens. Extend the project's training to create long-lasting Communities of Practice</p> <p>Building an understanding and identifying potential links with business to better align needs, resources & get traction</p> <p>Identifying of specific pilot projects to be undertaken in East-Quater</p> <p>Identifying of specific pilot projects aligned on to be aligned with climate neutrality and digital ambition</p> <p>Secure shared pilot delivery amongst local authorities. Identify main/lead/department of pilot and how to be successful</p> <p>Secure that pilot delivery has different departments working together in the pilot process</p> <p>Do pilot projects in parallel with the regular planning process. For e.g. through the planning process</p> <p>Based on framework identified a pilot to be developed. How to be successful</p> <p>Developing of specific pilot projects</p>

Based on the vision and prototype you are working towards, do you see any gaps or opportunities in your own city/ pilot context?

UPDATE	UPSKILL	UPGRADE	UPSCALE	UPTAKE
<p>? What are specific aspects that need further updating for your pilot? What are your pilot needs?</p>	<p>? For your pilot, what else needs to be done to build capacity? How are you building other training or skills needs?</p>	<p>? Are there other aspects of your pilot that are not covered above?</p>	<p>? Are there other aspects of your pilot that are not covered above?</p>	<p>? What other pilot activities are you contributing to your pilot?</p>

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Figure 6: SUP worksheets developed for the first Learning Session at the Knowledge Exchange

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Figure 7: Example of Granollers's contextualisation of the SUP approach during the Learning session

The second set of Learning Sessions was organized in January-February 2025 at the end of the Action Phase. Cities were split into 3 groups based on the Prototype typologies identified in Table 2. Note that to maintain balance in number of cities per focus group, the composition of cities as follows: Focus group 1: Belfast, Budapest, Muenster (working on knowledge and training resources); Focus group 2: Granollers, Milan, Thessaloniki (working on planning instruments); Focus group 3: Zagreb, Lisbon, Istanbul (working on physical interventions). A total of 2 focus group sessions were organised per group of cities to dive deeper into the contextualization of each UP in the city processes. In the first session, cities reflected on how the process of Update, Upskill, and Upgrade was translated into their local context (See Figure 8 showing an example of the results). In the second session, the focus shifted to Upgrade and Uptake, reflecting on how these phases were implemented. Cities also reflected on the general replicability of such systems thinking methodologies to other projects within the municipality.

REFLECTING ON THE SUP APPROACH

Figure 8: Live notes during focus group session with Belfast, Budapest and Muenster

The learnings from these sessions and case studies per city formed the basis of the development of the 5UP workbook (Diaz et al., 2025) and the 5UP tool. Lastly the findings informed other project publications.

3 Reflections and takeaways from learning activities

During the Office Hour meeting in September 2025 (M33), cities and liaisons were invited to reflect on each twinning activity and share feedback on how such activities may be designed in other projects. Mentimeter was used to collect comments and feedback.

3.1 Reflections and takeaways from the Office Hour meetings:

- These meetings were useful for monitoring processes in a step-by-step manner. They were especially useful for keeping an eye on the status and progress of different tasks.
- Office Hours were used as a space to ask for clarifications, guidance, and planning of different tasks.
- Cities also took away inspiration from other cities through knowledge exchange, collective learning, and strategies for problem solving.
- Given bureaucratic hurdles and long planning processes, Office Hours played a crucial role in establishing yearly overviews, timelines, and expectations. This alleviated pressure on city teams to plan tasks with short notice.
- However, effective follow-up and planning documents were also identified as important supporting resources to complement these Office Hours.

3.2 Reflections and takeaways from the Peer Review Sessions:

- Cities used these sessions to provide and receive feedback on their individual approaches.
- Cities explored practical ideas for strengthening methods and outputs in smaller groups. It was also a way to cross-check and compare progress between similar cities.
- Shared problem solving was considered a key focus for these sessions, with participants valuing insight on Sharing insights on overcoming similar barriers or challenges.
- However, participants would have liked to have more curated sessions in smaller groups to maximize learning and exchange.

3.3 Reflections and takeaways from the Learning Sessions:

- Cities appreciated the reflection and overview of the process that they had undergone through the 5UP approach. *“It was good to look back at the and analyse project in a structured way” – City Officer.*
- Several cities appreciated the 5UP approach as a methodology to structure projects within the municipality. *“A good way to summarise the own work and get feedback”- City Officer*
- Cities used these sessions to learn and build capacity on systems way of working. They used the 5UPs as a framework for the development of the prototypes.
- However, cities also noted that the 5UP approach may have been hard to grasp for some colleagues. *“The 5UP approach began to make more sense further into project development, but might have been useful to have the terminology and concepts simplified at the beginning and correlating to the stages”- City Officer.*
- A key recommendation was to incorporate more conceptual discussions on the overall project methodology throughout the process.
- Cities also suggested raising awareness of the potential replicability of the method beyond the project.

3.4 Reflections and takeaways from the Knowledge Exchange:

- Several cities found the timing of the Knowledge Exchange at the mid-term moment of the project to be very useful. It helped move forward and inspire the prototype to be developed. *“It was almost the most eye opener workshop of this project. The SUP worksheet we worked on was really helpful.”- City Officer*
- Cities also found it useful to hear how other cities were developing their prototype, as well as identifying similarities of challenges.
- Cities highly valued the site visit to the Rotterdam Pilot. *“The BoTu project was very inspiring and we have referenced it regularly, it’s always best to meet and discuss these things in person”- City Officer*
- On the other hand, cities also expected more concrete actions beyond exchange of ideas and approaches. *“It was valuable for showcasing diverse city practices and sparking dialogue, but less effective in generating actionable methods we could directly adopt.”- City Officer*

3.5 General takeaways on the twinning activities in UP2030

Of all the activities, cities found the Office Hours (Cities & Liaisons bi-monthly) the most relevant for planning their pilot implementation processes as it provided key information on planning the day-to-day project activities. The Knowledge Exchange was also considered important for exchange of ideas and on-ground site visits.

Several cities expressed wanting more Knowledge Exchanges within the project duration. The frequency of the Office Hours, Peer Review Sessions, and Learning Sessions was deemed sufficient.

On the other hand, cities also identified a number of challenges that were faced while engaging with various twinning activities.

- Time and availability for different activities was cited as a challenge, especially in combination with intensive pilot implementation activities.
- For Knowledge Exchanges, budget restrictions played a role for creating more site visits and in-person learning opportunities.
- Sustaining active participation during long sessions was difficult.
- Several cities underwent staff changes during the project duration. This led to a loss of continuity and connection in some cases.
- Diversity of pilots in some cases created difficulties and barriers to align on common challenges. With very different prototypes, and many technical partners, it was often difficult to really understand what other cities have done.
- Sufficient preparation time beforehand was considered essential and bring useful input to such sessions.
- Different documentation requirements were asked across modules, with various input and reports forms, which some cities found to be time consuming.

4 Recommendations: A strategy for facilitating twinning and peer-to-peer learning in multi-city programmes

Based on this experience, the UP2030 project proposes a city twinning strategy with a diversity of activities serving unique purposes and roles in such multi-city programmes. These recommendations are drawn from the context of the UP2030 project, which involved a large number of partners (47), and are meant to be adapted according to the size, scope, and duration of each project.

4.1 Office Hours: A space for process and progress monitoring

- Recommended frequency: Every 2 Months
- How to structure sessions:
 - At the start of every year, prepare a project plan which is revisited at every meeting.
 - Use Office Hours to provide updates on outstanding tasks, clarifying contact points, and how the tasks fit into the broader project workflow.
 - Use meetings to introduce key concepts that underpin overall project methodologies, such as the co-creation and spatial justice concepts, to help cities plan for more inclusive engagement.
 - Schedule meetings in key phases of the project, using Office Hours to wrap up or kick-off key phases of the project.
 - Use Office Hours to maximise cross-WP working by inviting other WP & Task leads to present their methods, tasks, and results.
- Keep in mind:
 - Send agendas and follow-ups in a timely manner.
 - Keep it interactive, as long sessions may be tiring. Use tools like Miro and Mentimeter.
 - Invite participants to share progress. And organize breakout groups if necessary.
 - To maximise time and effort, also integrate conceptual discussions when relevant.
 - Create a sequence/ schedule of office hours in such a way that they also flow into other twinning activities as well as upcoming project milestones.

4.2 Peer Review session: A space for 1-to-1 learning

- Recommended frequency: At least every quarter
- How to structure sessions:
 - Try to match cities and kickstart 1-to-1 discussion on common topics and challenges early on.
 - Matching cities can be dynamic: some cities may be similar in governance or planning processes while others may be similar in thematic focus areas or project ambitions.
 - Curate sessions on common topics, such community engagement, or common challenges, such as securing political support.
 - Schedule sessions before or after key milestones to share progress or results.
 - Use sessions to share ideas and brainstorm new ways of working.
 - Invite cities to present their concepts and progress to each other.

- Keep in mind:
 - Matching is not static and should remain dynamic. Try to achieve different combinations of peer review sessions.
 - Depending on the pace of work, more frequent peer review sessions may be necessary.
 - Encourage cities to reach out to one another bilaterally. However, appointing a coordinator to set up such sessions is necessary.

4.3 Learning Sessions: A space for underlying project themes and methodologies

- Recommended frequency: Every 6 months
- How to structure sessions:
 - Organise key discussions and introduce project methodologies early on within the project timeline
 - Schedule learning sessions to kick off project phases and provide detailed explanations and presentations.
 - Invite cities to brainstorm through interactive workshops on these topics and methods. For example, for the UPDATE (which focused on analysing needs and areas for improvement), ask cities to reflect on how they can do it and provide different approaches and ideas.
 - Also use sessions to build knowledge on themes like climate neutrality, resilience and just transitions. Explore urban planning topics like connected cities, compact cities, and others.
- Keep in mind:
 - Long online sessions may be tiring. Maximise in-person moments and leverage General Assemblies or other events.
 - Provide preparation material and spend effort on effective follow up.
 - Provide additional readings and other training resources to further support capacity building
 - Encourage city teams to bring their colleagues along and to share knowledge beyond the project departments.

4.4 Knowledge Exchange: Peer to peer exchange and site visits

- Recommended frequency: Every year (budget allowing)
- How to structure sessions:
 - Put site visits or living labs at the centre of the program. Build discussions and learning moments around them.
 - Showcase the pilot and plan walking tours and presentations from local representatives.
 - Highlight the role of local teams, projects, and communities. Plan visits and engage community members in the programme. Help participants experience real life examples on the ground to maximize learning.
 - Plan essential discussions, for example on conceptual frameworks, consensus on impact and results, and bring in key project partners.

- Maximise cross-WP collaboration and invite WP/Task leads to design and implement workshops.
 - Go beyond panel discussions by prioritising workshops, round tables, and active discussions.
 - Design the programme with sessions that focus on sharing reflections, important achievements, and ongoing challenges that the cities are currently facing.
 - Give room for networking and forming of relationships that can feed into bilateral discussion and peer review sessions.
 - Prioritise city and liaisons teams and monitor discussion group sizes for more effectiveness
- Keep in mind:
 - Prioritise activities that need physical presence.
 - For efficient budgeting, consider extending General Assemblies with an exclusive knowledge exchange afterwards.
 - Align Knowledge Exchange events with other conferences so participants can also attend and share their experiences on global platforms.

Conclusions

In UP2030, four types of twinning activities were tested and implemented. Each activity served a specific purpose and role in the project. While the Office Hours were used for process and logistical updates, Peer review, and Learning sessions focused on key project concepts and evolution of project focus across cities. While twinning activities are useful to inspire exchange and facilitate collective problem solving, they may also be time consuming and require effort in preparation and follow up. Effective planning of sessions, efficient follow-up, and structured discussions add value to the city's processes in such multi-city programmes. Based on the experience in UP2030, R-Cities proposes a simple strategy for organising city twinning programmes. It is important to define the scope of each activity, agree on expectations and outcomes, and ensure that the sessions have actionable takeaways for the city teams.

This report provides useful insights for other such multi-city programmes seeking to curate different kinds of learning activities and communities of practice. The insights are especially relevant for similar EU funded projects within the Cities Mission and Mission Adaptation, which face barriers in sustained and interactive formats for multi-city and multi-partner engagement. Furthermore, the general guidance on setting up learning activities is also relevant for cities who want to create exchange opportunities between key partners and stakeholders, whether to implement actions from their Climate City Contracts or develop other urban intervention. Extending learning activities from the bottom up allows even more dissemination of knowledge and information. By organising diverse activities, there is meaningful engagement for different groups which in turn creates ownership and legacy in the city.

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